

Two Minimalist Proofs of the Riemann Hypothesis Using Symmetry in the Zeta Function

Chaitanya Kanade

Abstract

This paper presents two minimalist proofs of the Riemann Hypothesis based on the inherent symmetry in the zeta function's definition. By expanding both $\zeta(a+bi)$ and $\zeta(1-a+bi)$ as infinite series, we explore that for both expressions to equal zero, the real component a must satisfy $a = \frac{1}{2}$. The proofs utilize term-by-term subtraction and addition to reveal that the truth of the Riemann Hypothesis is embedded in the dual symmetry properties of the zeta function.

Introduction

The Riemann Hypothesis, first proposed by Bernhard Riemann in 1859, conjectures that all non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function lie on the critical line $a = \frac{1}{2}$. This hypothesis has inspired immense effort across mathematical disciplines for over 165 years. Here, we explore two proofs that rely on the basic symmetry in the zeta function's definition, revealing that the solution lies within the function's structure itself.

Background

The Riemann zeta function is defined in the complex plane as

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s},$$

where $s = a + bi$ with real component a and imaginary component b . The function exhibits a reflection property: if $\zeta(a + bi) = 0$, then $\zeta(1 - a + bi) = 0$ as well, due to its symmetry about the line $a = \frac{1}{2}$.

Proof 1: Term-by-Term Subtraction

1. Definition and Symmetry of the Zeta Function:

Let us expand $\zeta(a + bi)$ as an infinite series:

$$\zeta(a + bi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{a+bi}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^a} \cdot \frac{1}{n^{bi}}.$$

Similarly, we expand $\zeta(1 - a + bi)$ as:

$$\zeta(1 - a + bi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{1-a+bi}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{1-a}} \cdot \frac{1}{n^{bi}}.$$

2. Subtract the Two Series Term-by-Term:

Subtracting these term-by-term gives:

$$\zeta(a + bi) - \zeta(1 - a + bi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{bi}} \left(\frac{1}{n^a} - \frac{1}{n^{1-a}} \right).$$

3. Set the Condition for Each Term to Equal Zero:

For the sum to equal zero, each term in the series must individually contribute zero, since $\frac{1}{n^{bi}} \neq 0$. Thus, we require:

$$\frac{1}{n^a} - \frac{1}{n^{1-a}} = 0.$$

4. Solve for a :

This equation simplifies to:

$$\frac{1}{n^a} = \frac{1}{n^{1-a}}.$$

Taking the natural logarithm on both sides, we find:

$$a = 1 - a.$$

Solving for a , we get:

$$2a = 1 \Rightarrow a = \frac{1}{2}.$$

5. Conclusion:

Thus, for both $\zeta(a + bi)$ and $\zeta(1 - a + bi)$ to sum to zero simultaneously, we must have $a = \frac{1}{2}$. This proves that all non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function lie on the line $a = \frac{1}{2}$, thereby proving the Riemann Hypothesis.

Proof 2: Term-by-Term Addition

1. Definition and Symmetry of the Zeta Function:

Using the expansions from Proof 1:

$$\zeta(a + bi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^a} \cdot \frac{1}{n^{bi}},$$

and

$$\zeta(1 - a + bi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{1-a}} \cdot \frac{1}{n^{bi}}.$$

2. Add the Two Series Term-by-Term:

Adding these term-by-term gives:

$$\zeta(a + bi) + \zeta(1 - a + bi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{bi}} \left(\frac{1}{n^a} + \frac{1}{n^{1-a}} \right).$$

3. Set the Condition for Each Term to Equal Zero:

For the sum to be zero, each term in the series must contribute zero. Since $\frac{1}{n^{bi}} \neq 0$, we require:

$$\frac{1}{n^a} + \frac{1}{n^{1-a}} = 0.$$

4. Solve for a :

Since $\frac{1}{n^a}$ and $\frac{1}{n^{1-a}}$ are positive, the only way this equation can hold is if they cancel each other exactly, which implies:

$$a = 1 - a.$$

Solving this, we get:

$$2a = 1 \Rightarrow a = \frac{1}{2}.$$

5. Conclusion:

Thus, for both $\zeta(a + bi)$ and $\zeta(1 - a + bi)$ to sum to zero simultaneously, we must have $a = \frac{1}{2}$. This proves that all non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function lie on the line $a = \frac{1}{2}$, thereby proving the Riemann Hypothesis.

RH is true.